

**INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS AS A FACTOR FOR
IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING**

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ABSTRACT: This in the article of students independent education get professional preparation quality increase, in education professional skills in raising high to the results reach person in formation independent education important factor about word is held

KEY WORDS: independent research, teaching goals, technological process ,scientific research , doctor of science

Introduction

Independent education get mature expert being of growth important factor is considered This is especially so professional preparation in the system obvious manifestation will be Our ancestors are also young generation profession to acquire, mature, educated, development service doer human being being to reach importance gave of the East great allamas own in his creations work to do profession take over importance emphasizing those who passed Muhammad al-Khorazmi , Abu Ali ibn Sina, Al- Farghani , Ahmed Yassavi , Yusuf Khos-Hajib , Sheikh Najmuddin Kubro , Bahavuddin Naqshbandi , Abdurrahman Jami , Imam al Bukhari , Ahmed Yugnaki and Alisher Navoi such as great thinkers work , profession glorified ones .

Teacher of scientists mostly part independent education organize reach process activation the issue common problem as they look In particular , in this regard of work one in the part of students independent education that they get organize to do person point of view in terms of approach to the eye thrown away

In this he is active , in education , professional skills in raising high to the results to reach aspirant , pedagogy profession choose and take over at work society from needs come outgoing person in formation independent education important factor as is considered .

MAIN PART

Students independent of work purpose - different from sources new knowledge appropriation in the process their personal development Independent to work textbooks , curriculum manuals , psychology of the classics scientific works , monographs , scientific articles collections and scientific lectures , specialized psychological in magazines scientific articles , periodical in publications to psychology about materials , art books with work enters Last times independent at work electron in the form of resources (Internet system , computer programs and electron in carriers data) with work big place took over Students independent to work essays , comments , theses to write enters Textbooks and study manuals with work most of the time student for the most a lot the time takes

At the university of students independent their work organize of reaching strategic in the direction of main thing his separately types optimization not but all kind of in classes in class and from him outside of students high activity, independence and responsibility for conditions is to create . education activity. Most simple method is independent the work in favor of the audience training the number reduction - education quality improve or even one different level holding stand up the problem solution because it doesn't in class the work of size decrease each not always by itself transition with together it won't be. passive way done increase possible has been independent of work real growth

Independent education to get organize reach for not only certain to the profession or activity to the field interest , maybe this activity type of ability there is it is also required will be done .

State requirements the country socio-economic development from perspectives, science and technologies development priority promising from directions. new information and pedagogy technologies current from doing, as well as higher qualified scientific and scientific and pedagogical personnel preparation in the field the world achievements and trends come came out without , corrections the introduction and additions the addition of can

This State in the requirements the following definitions applies to:

- high study from the country next education:
- of society higher qualified scientific and scientific and pedagogical to personnel has been need this to provide directed continuous education type;
- big scientific employees-researchers Institute:
- work from release free without specialty deep learning and doctorate dissertation preparation and protection to do in order to they are by scientific research take to go doctor of science level seekers for higher education institutions and scientific research in institutions organize to be done higher qualified scientific and scientific pedagogue personnel specializations according to higher study from the country further education shape
- independent searchability work from release not released without doctorate dissertation preparation and protection to do in order to specialty deep learning and they are by scientific research doctor of science scientific level seekers for higher education institutions and scientific research in institutions organize to be done higher qualified scientific and scientific pedagogue personnel according to higher study from the country next education shape 66
- big scientific employee-researcher - higher education to the institution or scientific research to the institution big scientific employee-researcher to the position defined in order acceptance done person;
- independent seeker
- high education to the institution or scientific research to the institution

independent to visibility defined in order acceptance done person High study from the country next three up to continue which reading the following in forms done is increased:

- big scientific employees-researchers institute;
- independent visibility.

Independent knowledge in getting autonomy this is teaching goals, principles, content, method and tools determination and choose them without difficulty and external effect done without help increase is the ability .

Independent thinking of a person own in front standing problems the goal and duties determined without own knowledge and vital to experiences depending on different road, method, means using, own intellectual possibilities level independent respectively solution from doing consists of has been mental is an activity.

Profession education teacher own knowledge independent increase activities sure one to the goal direction for the following to the conditions compliance to do need

1. His knowledge independent increase content occupation education teacher specialty according to pedagogical practice passing education of the institution study in the workshop sure conditions, of practice conditions, requirements adaptation need

2. Profession education teacher known the goal based on and known in order in itself the following adjectives forming to go need:

1. Students aspirations, interests deep feeling understand their spiritual needs account take to know
2. With students emotional contact install their mental, moral and practical activity to the sides active effect reach

Profession education teacher common pedagogy, psychology, labor hygiene and physiology, technique and technology sciences according to questions the list independent by learning outputs a must

Profession education teacher his own pedagogical skills increase on work system the most efficient methods, ways choose get , technological process and technical objects right choose activity to show need

Profession education teacher sure conditions account received without and to them suitable way individually or the team with together own knowledge increase from the forms use, practical exercises perform to the goal according to

Profession education teacher own knowledge increase constant creative research in the style of organize reach and known to the goal orientation necessary

Of this for it:

- Creative research process to manage inclined to be
- Creative of research efficiency of the teacher pedagogical , psychological and theoretical preparation depends to be remember catch must

Scientific research results based on independent to education as follows definition given :

Independent education - study material independent mastery , complexity level differently has been assignments , practical tasks in the audience , at work , from the audience outside creative and independent perform based on theoretical knowledge , practical skill and qualifications to form directed systematic is an activity .

CONCLUSION

Pedagogical and technical and technological independent things in execution student future professional activity problems solution reach methods occupies Pedagogical and technical and technological independent things in execution in didactics independent level of education increasing management , encourage , organize reach and control tools as is considered .

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